

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18813651>

**Impact of Katsina Youth Craft Center on Sustainability of Small-Scale Enterprises
Katsina State, Nigeria**

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted on impact of Katsina Youth Craft Centre (KYCC) on sustainability of small-scale enterprises in Katsina State. Based on the study, three specific objectives were targeted, three research questions were raised, and three null hypotheses were also formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 10,000 graduates (2015-2019) from Katsina Youth Craft Centre. Based on the nature of the graduates' population, 371 graduates were selected and served as sample size of the study. Four points rating scale structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while analysis of variance was used to answer the null hypotheses. The findings of the study among others revealed that skills development training provided by the KYCC had a significant impact on the sustainability of small-scale enterprises among graduates of 3, 6, 9- and 12-month course durations in the study area, based on the evidence from the study. Hence, it was concluded that KYCC had impact on the sustainability on small-scale enterprises in Katsina State. The researcher recommends among others that, in addition to vocational skills training courses taught, accounting and marketing courses should be introduced at the center.

Keywords: Katsina Youth Craft Centre (KYCC), Small-Scale Enterprises, Vocational Education, Youth Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Globalisation had turned the world into entity whereby, transforming markets into a single market place. Economic development increases the demand for expertise and a high-quality workforce across society, resulting in a new phase of development in vocational education. A competent workforce is essential for competitive profitability in the global marketplace. The development of vocational education and training has become one of the most important strategies in both developing and developed countries. Vocational education is particularly important for promoting economic development, expanding employment size, and improving the quality of employment. Governments around the world are currently undertaking reforms in their education and training systems to meet the demand for an appropriately skilled workforce in an evolving global economy. European Training Foundation (2021).

Katsina Youth Craft Centre was established in 2014 by the Katsina State House of Assembly under Section 12 to provide courses of study, training, or skills development as well as any other sphere of learning approved by the board for the purpose of self-employment and by granting the graduates with Certificates in vocational training. The centre offers courses of study that will improve job mobility, career development, progressive academic articulation, and the source of motivation for the students. Promote, through teaching and other means, the advancement of knowledge and its practical application to the needs of the community. The youth craft centre was also designed to provide self-employment opportunities to over 2000 youth annually throughout the state through various skill acquisition programmes and trades that are taught at the centre. This enables the graduates to establish small scale enterprises and be self-reliant.

The skills obtained at the centre with different time duration of 3, 6, 9, and 12 months are: Leather works and shoe making, Film and photography; Beauty salon, GSM handset repairs, tie and dye, pottery, wrought iron and furniture making, catering services, tailoring and fashion design, computer repairs/usage, auto mechanic/generator repairs, wheel alignment and balancing, welding fabrication and blacksmithing, carpentry, and joinery in vocational skill education. The KYCC also provides access to finance and market opportunities, enabling young people to start and sustain their small-scale enterprises.

Small-scale enterprises play a crucial role in the economic development of Katsina State, providing employment opportunities and contributing to the growth of the state's economy. However, small-scale enterprises in the state face numerous challenges such as limited access to finance, infrastructure, and market opportunities. The KYCC aims to address some of these challenges by providing training, mentoring, and access to finance and market opportunities for young people. Small scale enterprises are the most common form of business in Nigeria. The aim of any economy (either industrialised or not) depends largely on how well it manages its small-scale industries (Etebefia & Akinkumi, 2013). To have a successful business enterprise, skills need to be acquired and sustained for a lifetime.

Skill acquisition can be defined as the form of training by individuals or groups of individuals that can lead to the acquisition of knowledge for self-sustenance. It involves the training of people in different fields of trade under a legal agreement between the trainers and the trainees for a certain duration and under certain conditions. Skill acquisition is also the process of demonstrating the habit of active thinking or behaviour in a specific activity. Skill acquisition is, however, seen as the ability to do or perform an activity that is related to some meaningful exercise, work, or job. For skill to be acquired, appropriate knowledge, attitudes, habits and qualities of character must be learned to enable the acquirer to develop intellectual, emotional, and moral character, which prepares the individual for a brighter future (Alkire & Samman, 2021). Skill acquisition as a means of youth empowerment has caught the government's attention in Nigeria for over two decades. This is so because it is believed that exposing youth to skill acquisition programmes will reduce youth unemployment and enhance their self-sustenance. Vocational skills are referred to as "basic," according to this research work. Basic vocational skills are practical or first-hand skills that help a person master a trade or a job in their small-sale enterprise (Deming, 2017), this can lead to sustainability of the business.

Sustainability in this context is the ability for the graduates of Katsina Youth Craft Centre to endure all the challenges of the environment by applying the acquired basic vocational skills to make the business successful for a lifetime and to be self-reliant by creating a small-scale business for self-development and society. Sustainability requires meeting the pressing needs of all people and extending opportunities to satisfy their aspirations for a better life (Ndubuisi-Okolo, Anekwe, & Attah, 2016). Poverty alleviation, youth empowerment, entrepreneurship development, self-reliance and effective leadership are perceived as key strategies for actualising the four key components of sustainability (environment, economic, social, and political) in Nigeria. A critical look at the population explosion in the country vitiates the vision of achieving sustainable skill acquisition development in Nigeria. Kram (2019). The variables so far discussed constitute the background of this study on the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre on the sustainability of Small-Scale Enterprises, Nigeria.

Despite the positive impact of the KYCC on small-scale enterprises in Katsina State, there was the need to assess the sustainability of the skills acquired at the center and its impact on small-scale enterprises established by the graduates in the state. It was against this background that this work was undertaken to empirically investigate the possible impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre on the sustainability of Small-Scale Enterprises, Nigeria.

Vocational training is extremely important in Skill development, Career advancement, Economic growth, Social mobility and Personal development. Vocational training is a crucial component of education and workforce development, and it benefits individuals, industries, and society as a whole.

The relationship between vocational training and the Katsina Youth Craft Center is that the center provides vocational training to young people in Katsina and surrounding areas. The vocational training offered at the center is aimed at equipping young people with the practical skills they need to become self-employed or gain employment in various industries.

The center provides hands-on training, workshops, and apprenticeships to young people in various vocational fields. Through vocational training at the center, young people can gain the skills and knowledge they need to start their own businesses or work.

Katsina Youth Craft Centre trains, certifies and graduate students with basic vocational training in various trades within a set time frame on the trade or course, making them productive and self-reliant towards the general development of the state and the nation. The researcher discovered that, from the students' records obtained from Katsina youth craft centre, in 2016 academic session that were engaged in small scale business after graduation, 37% were still in the business, while 63% of the businesses that were established failed and also, those that are not engaged in any business failed to secure a job from the government and other private organisations. In 2017 academic session, 35% of graduates from Katsina youth craft centre were still working in small size entrepreneurial enterprises, while 65% of established businesses were unable to get a job in order to be self-sufficient members of society. It is based on this problem, the researcher conducted a preliminary survey in Katsina, Funtua, and Daura Local Government Areas, selecting 120 graduates from the KYCC in 2017 and 2018. Only 36 graduates, representing 30% of the graduates from different trades, enterprises, and businesses succeeded, while 84 graduates, representing 70% of the graduates with established small-scale enterprises, failed. This results to an engagement and debate with both those who succeeded and those who did not. The researcher's engagement with the graduates revealed that neither the government nor the vocational training centre had made much effort to investigate the likely causes of these enterprises' failure.

Based on these, the researcher decided to conduct a study on the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre on the sustainability of Small-Scale Business Enterprises in Nigeria, using the vocational centre policy document as a foundation. In order to determine the significant impact of the centre being it one of the government owned institution that trained skill acquisition programmes in the state.

The general objective of the study was to assess the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre on the sustainability of Small-Scale enterprises in Katsina State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study were to:

The findings of this study after publication in journals and other media would be of importance to students/graduates of the centre, Katsina Youth Craft Centre, teachers\instructors, the community where the centre is situated (Katsina State), the state government (as the sponsor and curriculum designers), further researchers, and other small-scale business trainers as follows:

The study would be of significance to the students/graduates of Katsina Youth Craft Centre in the management of the small-scale enterprise business. Students/graduates would benefit from the findings of the study, as the results would help them determine the factors that would have a positive impact on their careers. Also, the study would aid them in their career choices.

Katsina Youth Craft Centre would benefit from this study through the impact of achieving its objectives and by making the graduates self-reliant and ready to be exposed in the market to run and sustain the business successfully.

The study would also be significant to the teachers\instructors of the centre in improving the basic vocational skills in preparing their lesson plans, their lectures, and the way they train the students to face the societal business challenges.

The State Government Ministry of Education, as the curriculum planners of the centre, would use the study to add the outcome of the study to the curriculum of the centre because the result would solve some of the challenges faced by some graduates of the centre of not sustaining their businesses beyond two years of its existence.

The study would be very significant to the community in the sense that the graduates will be able to establish businesses that would be successful and have a long life, where new technology will be used to advance products that would lead to competition and reduced importation.

The state government would use the study to improve the curriculum of the school and incorporate the positive outcome of the study. Also, the state government, as the initiator and sponsor of the centre, would benefit from having self-reliant youth and a skilled society.

Other small-scale schools/trainers and small-scale enterprise across the country would use the study effectively in their training for sustainable small-scale enterprise in their organisations.

Also, some researchers would use the study to conduct further researches on the development of small and medium enterprises in society.

There were many theories related to this research work. The researcher decided to use vocational skills theory founded by Donald Edwin Super, an American psychologist who is known for his research on vocational development. Super developed his theory in 1953 and it has since become one of the most influential models for understanding how individuals choose and develop their skill careers. Super's theory of vocational development emphasizes the importance of self-concept, career maturity, and life roles in skill career decision-making, and has been widely applied in educational and counseling settings.

Vocational skills theory is a psychological theory that explains how individuals acquire and develop skills necessary for work and career success. The theory posits that vocational skills are acquired through a combination of factors, including personal aptitudes, interests, and abilities, as well as environmental factors such as education and work experience.

According to the theory, vocational skills are hierarchical and build upon each other, with basic skills such as training, reading and writing providing the foundation for more complex skills. The theory recognizes the importance of job-specific skills, such as technical knowledge and training, in achieving career success.

Vocational skills theory suggests that individuals can enhance their vocational skills through education, training, and work experience. It also emphasizes the importance of self-awareness and self-assessment in identifying one's strengths and weaknesses, and in making informed career decisions.

Vocational skills theory provides a framework for understanding how individuals develop the skills necessary to succeed in the workforce, and highlights the importance of ongoing learning and skill development in achieving career success.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is shown in Figure 1, which indicates the figurative connection of the variables. It explains the interaction between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The independent variable in this study was Katsina Youth Craft Centre, while the dependent variable was the sustainability of Small-Scale Enterprise.

Conceptual Framework Chart

Figure 1: A schematic connection of the variables of the study Source: (Uzoagulu, 2011)

Katsina Youth Craft Centre

The Katsina Youth Craft Centre is a vocational training center established by the Katsina State Government in Nigeria to provide young people with skills and knowledge to start and sustain small scale enterprises. The Centre offers training programs in various craft and vocational skills, including tailoring, welding, carpentry, leatherwork, and computer skills.

The youth craft centre is designed to provide self-employment opportunities to over 2000 youth annually throughout the state through the various skills acquisition programmes mentioned below, and 14 trades are taught at the centre. As of June 2016, over 5,000 youth were trained on different skill acquisition programmes and are presently scattered across the state. It also consists of well-equipped workshops, each representing particular trades, seven additional shades for outdoor activities,

administrative block; hostel accommodation for over 2000 youth (both male and female), generator house; and a borehole.

The centre has the following. The 14 numbers of trades and durations are as follows

3. Month duration training

- a. Leather work and shoe making
- b. Film and photograph
- c. Beauty salon

6. Months duration of training

- a. GSM handset repairs
- b. Tie and dye
- c. Pottery
- d. Wrought iron and furniture making
- e. Catering services
- f. Tailoring and fashion design

7. Month duration training

Computer repairs/usage

8. Month duration trainings

- a. Auto mechanic/generator repairs
- b. Wheel alignment and balancing
- c. Welding, fabrication, and blacksmithing
- d. Carpentry and joinery

Skill development

According to Simon McGrath and Jo-Anna (2023) Skill development refers to the process of acquiring or improving skills and knowledge that are necessary to perform a particular job or task. It involves developing technical, cognitive, and social skills that enable individuals to perform their work effectively and efficiently.

Skill development take place through formal education and training programs, on-the-job training, apprenticeships, and other forms of learning. It can also involve continuous learning and upskilling to keep up with changing technologies and job requirements.

Skill development is important for individuals, organizations, and economies as a whole. For individuals, skill development can lead to better job opportunities, higher wages, and greater job satisfaction. For organizations, it can lead to greater productivity, improved quality, and higher profits. For economies, skill development can lead to increased competitiveness, innovation, and economic growth. United Nations Development Program (2022).

Small-Scale Enterprises

A small scale enterprise is a business that is typically owned and operated by a small number of individuals and has relatively low turnover and assets compared to larger businesses. Small scale enterprises are often classified based on their number of employees, annual revenue, and level of capital investment.

Small scale enterprises can be found in a wide range of industries and sectors, including agriculture, manufacturing, retail, and services. They may operate as sole proprietorships, partnerships, or small corporations (Kehinde et al., 2016).

Small scale enterprises are important to the economy because they contribute to job creation, income generation, and economic growth. They are often more flexible and adaptable than larger businesses, allowing them to respond quickly to changing market conditions and customer needs. Small scale enterprises also play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship and innovation, as they provide opportunities for individuals to start and grow their own businesses Kehinde, Abiodu, Adegbuy, and Oladimeji (2016).

The contributions of small-scale enterprises to the economy cannot be overemphasised. Besides contributing significantly to reducing unemployment, it forms an avenue centre of the nations' economy because it generates a significant percentage of domestic taxes, produces goods and services using large

numbers of labour from the low to middle income categories of citizens; and supplies the goods and services to the general population. In a nutshell, small scale business enterprises represent the largest proportion of the productive population and by extension provide the avenue that keeps the economy running towards technological, economic, political and social development (MOPFED) Report cited in Kehinde et al., 2016).

Sustainability of Small Scale Enterprises Business

Sustainability, in my view refers to the ability to maintain or support something over the long term. In the context of business, sustainability refers to the ability of an enterprise to achieve long-term success while minimizing negative impacts on the environment, society, and economy. Sustainability involves balancing economic, social, and environmental considerations in decision-making and operations. This includes the responsible use of natural resources, the reduction of waste and pollution, the promotion of social equity and inclusion, and the creation of economic value for all stakeholders. Sustainability is important for businesses and society as a whole because it ensures that resources are used in a way that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable businesses are more resilient and better able to adapt to changing market conditions and customer preferences. They also contribute to a healthier and more equitable society and environment Ibrahim (2020).

Sustainability is needed to enhance the quality of the lives of citizens in a country. Ndbuisi, Okolo, Anekwe, and Attah (2016). In view of this, poverty alleviation, youth empowerment, entrepreneurship development, self-reliance and effective leadership are perceived as key strategies for actualizing the four key components of sustainable development (environment, economic, social, and political) in Nigeria. A critical look at the population explosion in the country vitiates the vision of achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. The quest for a sustainable economy is not feasible without alleviating poverty drastically, empowering the youth, encouraging entrepreneurship education for effective self-reliance etc., considering the latest trending issues of the population explosion, ranging from 139 million in the year 2005 to a whopping 189 million in 2016 Iwala, (2017). In the course of this study, a number of empirical studies were reviewed.

Okoli and Okeke (2018) investigated the need to ensure the success of small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) for sustainability and national development. The study ascertained the extent to which owners of Small and Medium Scale enterprises adopt financial management practices in Anambra State. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population comprised 2502 owners of small and medium scale enterprises who were registered with the Anambra State Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Technology. A validated structured questionnaire with a reliability coefficient index value of 0.84 using Cronbach alpha was used to collect data. Mean rating and standard deviation were used to analyse data collected while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used in testing the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings of the study revealed financial management practices such as establishing financial plans for specified areas of fund allocation and verifying record of accounting figures regularly were adapted to a low extent by the owners of SMEs in Anambra State. It was also discovered that years of business experience of the owners did not significantly affect their mean ratings to the extent of their adoption of the financial management practices in their businesses. It was concluded that the extent of adoption of financial management practices among the owners of SMEs in Anambra State was low. It was recommended among others that entrepreneurial bodies such as the National Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (NASME) should organise their members coherently with a view to guiding them through dissemination of relevant and up-to-date information on the identified financial management practices needed for business success.

This study has specific relevance to the current researchers work in the areas of small-scale business sustainability towards national development and financial management. The study adopted the same research design. However, the results of Okoli and Okeke were relevant in discussing the findings of this present study.

Miller and Eluro (2018) conducted a study on the Impact of information communication technology (ICT) on communication networks in small and medium enterprises, Delta state. Consequently, three (3) research objectives, three (3) research questions and three (3) testable

hypotheses were used in the study. The sample for the study comprised managers of registered Small and Medium scale industries with the State Ministry of Commerce. The questionnaire is the main instrument of data collection for the study. Data collected is analysed using mean, z-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Findings include that the utilisation of electronic mail (e-mail) by managers of SMEs is fairly adequate; the usage of voice is low while on-line Discussion of communication networks is barely applicable. It is recommended that the use of email be increased, while online discussion and video conferencing be applied to a higher degree, helps to increase customer reach, enhance sales, and create real new market grounds.

Research Design

The research design used for this study was survey research design. This design was considered appropriate to the study because of its procedures in qualitative research and researchers administer it to a population sample or to the entire population to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviours or characteristics of the population. This research design has the advantage of measuring current attitudes or practices. This was in line with Alamu and Olukosi (2010) who stated that survey research design enables the researcher to collect all data for the purpose of describing and interpreting existing conditions prevailing practices, beliefs, attitudes and on-going process. Kerlinger (1975) also advised that, this design should be employed when a research work involves the use of questionnaire to seek opinion of respondents.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised ten thousand three hundred and forty-seven graduates from all the 34 Local Government Areas of Katsina State who benefitted from the training at the Katsina Youth Craft Centre between 2015-2019. The sample size for the study was three hundred and seventy (370) graduates from Katsina Youths Craft Centre Katsina State, Nigeria. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the respondents for this research work. This sampling technique was adopted because the respondents were stratified according to training groups. The sample for the study from three most populous Local Government Areas (Katsina, Funtua, and Daura) with high economic activity is three hundred and seventy one (371) who were proportionally selected based on the population of each training group and strata using Research Advisor Sample Determination Table (2016). This is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Sample of the Study

L.G.A	2015				2016				2017				2018				2019				GT
	3m	6m	9m	12m																	
Begna	30	22	10	6	33	19	13	7	31	15	12	6	29	13	10	5	34	22	12	9	338
Baure	18	11	6	4	21	14	9	8	18	15	13	11	23	10	7	6	29	17	9	6	256
Batsari	20	13	8	6	23	16	11	9	21	16	11	13	25	11	6	4	30	18	7	5	273
Bakori	19	12	9	7	20	15	10	7	22	18	9	4	21	12	5	3	24	16	10	7	280
Sindawa	16	9	8	3	21	11	6	2	18	16	8	4	19	14	4	2	22	17	7	4	228
Daura	38	30	14	11	39	24	20	13	34	20	15	13	44	28	15	11	40	32	14	11	478
Dauja	18	12	7	5	20	15	8	4	19	16	8	5	18	9	6	4	21	11	7	5	218
Dussumma	34	25	14	11	35	20	15	9	30	25	11	10	40	24	11	8	36	28	12	7	405
Dandume	20	10	5	3	20	10	6	2	18	12	8	4	21	12	6	5	18	18	10	5	213
Dutsi	21	9	8	3	19	11	7	3	19	11	7	3	23	10	7	4	19	15	12	3	213
Darambana	18	11	6	4	21	14	9	8	19	14	10	14	23	10	7	5	29	17	9	6	254
Funtua	42	32	15	13	43	28	24	17	38	24	19	17	48	32	19	18	44	36	20	13	534
Faskari	15	8	4	1	19	12	10	6	14	9	3	2	16	11	8	3	13	8	6	4	172
Ingawa	14	9	5	2	17	11	9	3	15	9	6	3	14	8	5	2	16	10	7	5	170
Jiba	18	12	9	5	22	20	14	5	20	18	10	7	19	17	5	3	21	7	10	3	250
Katsina	49	40	26	12	55	31	45	27	30	48	43	18	49	47	30	15	51	40	23	12	751
Kafur	21	15	12	6	25	21	15	6	23	20	15	8	21	19	10	5	23	30	13	6	313
Kankia	38	25	20	10	42	38	32	20	49	38	33	15	38	37	28	14	40	45	38	14	655
Kuafi	18	16	12	6	21	18	12	7	19	17	12	8	18	32	7	4	20	26	19	10	302
Kankara	21	20	13	7	20	20	14	5	18	16	11	8	17	15	6	3	19	10	15	6	264
Rutada	17	21	11	6	21	17	11	4	19	13	10	6	18	14	5	4	17	15	5	3	239
Kalfa	15	12	9	5	19	15	9	4	17	16	8	8	16	15	4	8	18	9	9	6	220
Masoi	20	32	15	8	23	20	14	7	21	20	10	9	20	19	5	4	25	20	11	5	369
Makarfi	32	30	25	12	36	32	26	13	34	32	18	14	33	31	9	3	35	15	21	11	462
Mandaua	19	11	8	4	22	21	15	10	20	19	13	9	19	18	6	3	21	14	12	8	272
Charanci	16	10	6	3	20	18	12	8	18	20	10	10	17	19	7	6	20	10	13	7	250
Mari	30	23	16	8	33	30	24	12	31	29	19	13	30	28	11	9	27	4	8	6	391
Musawa	21	18	13	7	24	21	15	7	22	20	9	11	21	19	4	6	23	14	10	5	290
Matazu	18	15	11	5	22	20	14	7	20	18	8	7	19	17	5	4	22	18	9	4	263
Rimi	15	9	7	4	17	20	14	8	15	17	7	5	16	16	6	4	19	31	17	3	250
Sandamu	19	20	8	4	23	19	13	6	21	19	9	6	20	18	5	3	17	20	7	3	260
Sallama	20	14	7	3	24	21	15	9	22	20	9	4	21	19	11	6	23	15	9	5	277
Sakawa	14	10	6	6	18	16	10	5	16	15	6	4	15	14	8	6	20	13	6	2	210
Zargo	13	12	5	3	17	15	5	4	15	12	3	3	14	11	7	5	15	11	3	3	176
	757	569	394	202	855	673	486	272	778	658	408	202	805	629	295	193	851	622	401	213	10347

Source Population of this study. (2015 to 2019)

From the Table 2. The entire population for the study is 10347 that comprise 5 years graduates between 2015 and 2019 where 371 graduates were used as sample to represent the entire population of the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire named “Vocational Skills Sustainability Questionnaire” (VSSQ) developed by the researcher as seen in Appendix III. The instrument was used to obtain data from the graduates of the centre. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A sought information on respondents’ personal information. Section ‘B’ is a 24 questionnaire items designed to gather data to answer the research questions. Items 1 - 8 sought data to answer research question one, items 9 - 16 sought data to answer research question two, items 17 - 24 sought data to answer research question three. Items on the questionnaire were rated using four-point rating scale as Strongly Agree = 4 points, agree = 3 points, disagree = 2 points and Strongly Disagree = 1 point.

Procedure for Data Analysis

In analysing the data collected, frequencies and percentage were used to analyse the bio-data of the respondents. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the three research questions. A mean score of 2.5 and above was used as bench mark for “sustainable” while a mean score below 2.5 was used as bench mark for “unsustainable”. All the Null hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance in order to assess the impact of the significant difference among the enterprises on sustainability. In the analysis, if P value is less than 0.05 level of significant then the null hypothesis was rejected. On the other hand, when P value is greater than 0.05 level of significant then the null hypothesis was accepted. All the null hypotheses were rejected and draw findings at chapter four of this study.

Summary of Findings

From the data analysis the following were the summary of the findings of this study:

1. That the graduates of Katsina Youth Craft Centre skill development differ in different levels due to time durations and discipline on the sustainability of small-scale enterprises ($P < 0.05$).
2. That the graduates of Katsina Youth Craft Centre job mobility differed in different levels as a result of time durations and discipline on the sustainability of small-scale enterprises ($P < 0.05$).
3. That the graduates of Katsina Youth Craft Centre career development differed in different levels considering the time durations and discipline on the sustainability of small-scale enterprises ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one in table 3 and null hypothesis one in table 12 revealed that, graduates in different level of durations and discipline differ significantly in the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre for skills development on sustainability of small-scale enterprises among graduates of 3, 6, 9- and 12-months course duration in Katsina State Nigeria. This finding agreed with the report of Amadi and Opara (2018) that investigated on the Systems Approach to Entrepreneurial Education: A Panacea to Business Skills in Nigeria Tertiary Institution. The study adopted the systematic approach to examine the operational impact between the variable’s entrepreneurship education and acquisition of business skills in Nigeria tertiary institution. The results revealed clearly that there is a significant impact between entrepreneurship education and business skills measured. The study cited that entrepreneurship education improves students’ business planning skill in institution because it exposes students to a lot of business ideas which can be used to plan their dream business. It also recommended that entrepreneurship education should be more of practical than theoretical because students tend to remember and retain more of what they practice than what they read.

Wordu, Victor and Johnbull (2018) study also highlighted in Vocational Skills Acquisition for Entrepreneurship Development and Technological Advancement in Industrial Technology Education as a Strategic Approach to surmount Economic Recession in Nigeria. On the other hand, this finding did not agree with Chijioke and Iko (2018) that reported problems constraining acquisition of practical skills by

students of technical colleges in Kogi State included difficulties in Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) participation and inadequate workshop facilities.

Another findings of research question 2 in table 4 and null hypothesis 2 in table 13 Indicated that, graduates in different level of durations and discipline differ significantly in the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre for Job Mobility on sustainability of small-scale enterprises among graduates of 3, 6, 9- and 12-months course duration in Katsina State Nigeria. This finding agreed with the study of Teibowei and Osusu (2018) which found that the extent to which skills acquisition program is carried out in Bayelsa state is low; the extent to which people in Bayelsa state enrol for skill acquisition program is very poor and the extent to which people in Bayelsa state utilize skill acquisition program for self-sustenance and job creation is discouraging. Abdul (2018), also, found that entrepreneurial skills have a significant influence on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria and the UK. On the other hand, the findings did not agree with Mwila, (2016) who revealed that the poor state of infrastructure, poor implementation of the curriculum and inadequate funding resulted in the mismatch between the training offered and what was demanded on the labour market.

The findings of research question 3 in table 5 and null hypothesis 3 in table 14 demonstrated that, graduates in different level of durations and discipline differ significantly in the impact of the Katsina Youth Craft Centre for career development on sustainability of small-scale enterprises among graduates of 3, 6, 9- and 12-months course duration in Katsina State Nigeria. This finding agreed with the report of the study of Entrepreneurial skills and growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): A comparative analysis of Nigerian entrepreneurs and Minority entrepreneurs in the UK by Abdul, (2018), he investigated the significance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to an economy development of a country.

The study findings were that entrepreneurial skills have a significant influence on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria and the UK. However, the respondent in Nigeria and the UK agreed that creative thinking, Problem solving and communication skills are critical for increase sales and competitive advantage. Moreover, the respondent in Nigeria strongly agrees that high level of creative thinking with a bit of problem solving and communication skills will SMEs growth. By contrast, UK minority entrepreneurs argue that great creative thinking and a balance of problem solving and communication skills are critical to SMEs growth. Also, Amadi and Opara (2018) investigated on the Systems Approach to Entrepreneurial Education: A Panacea to Business Skills in Nigeria Tertiary Institution. The study revealed clearly that there is a significant impact between entrepreneurship education and business skills measured.

The study concluded that vocational training improves students 'business planning skill in institution because it exposes students to a lot of business ideas which can be used to plan their dream business. It also recommended that entrepreneurship education should be more of practical than theoretical because students tend to remember and retain more of what they practice than what they read. Gidado (2014) revealed that effective use of book-keeping/accounting, marketing, office technology and management, leadership and business management skills influenced the success and survival of SMEs in Nigeria. On the other hand, the findings did not agree with Chijioke and Iko (2018) which revealed that some of the problems constraining acquisition of practical skills by students of technical colleges in Kogi State included difficulties in Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) participation and inadequate workshop facilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings the study concluded that vocational training at the Katsina Youth Craft Centre has played a critical role in promoting sustainability among graduates of the center. Hence, the researcher concluded that Katsina Youth Craft Centre has impact on sustainability of small scale enterprises in Katsina State since the acquisition of practical skills and knowledge that the graduates have enabled them to establish and sustain small-scale enterprises in various fields, including tailoring, carpentry, and welding, among others. By implication, lack of vocational training at Katsina Youth Craft Centre will not enable the youths to sustain small scale enterprises.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made by the researcher:

- a. In addition to vocational skills training courses taught, accounting and marketing courses should be introduced at the centre and by business educators for the business to be well coordinated and well known to the community and larger society for the development of the small scale business in Katsina State.
- b. The graduates should move from one location to another to find out where the small scale enterprise would be sustained. To move from where there is low patronage to a higher patronage location.
- c. The graduates should advance their skills by attending workshops, seminars or take a course from polytechnic for a better career development.

REFERENCES

- Abdul, O. E. (2018), Entrepreneurial Skills and Growth of Small and Medium Enterprise. (S.M.Es): A Compartment Analysis of Nigeria Entrepreneur and Minority Entrepreneur in the *U.K International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences (IJARBSS) V8-15/4083*.
- Alamu, J.F. & Olukosi, J.O. (2010). *Simplified Research Methodology: Principles and Practice*. Zaria: Great Glory Publishers.
- Amadi and Opara (2014), Entrepreneurial Skills and Self-employment: A theoretical Explosion. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (I.J.S.B.E.R) vol. 10 No.2 PP 16-35*.
- Ayozie, D. O., Jacob, S. O., Umukoro, F., & Ayozie, V. U. (2013). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, The Marketing Interface. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research Marketing*, 13(9), 1-13.
- Alani, R. A., & Ojo, O. F. (2019). Small and medium enterprises and youth employment in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 7(1), 1-12.
- Alani, R. A., & Ojo, O. F. (2020). Sustainable small and medium enterprises in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 8(1), 1-14.
- Alkire, S., & Samman, E. (2021). Inclusive growth and development: the role of vocational education and training. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 25(1), 1-19.
- Antonelli, G., & De Liddo, A. (2021). Vocational education and training in the digital era: A review of the literature. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 73(3), 305-328.
- Boudard, E. A., & Lerman, R. I. (2019). Vocational education and training in the United States. In *Handbook of Vocational Education and Training* (pp. 1-23). Springer.
- Cedefop (2022). Vocational education and training in Europe – Luxembourg. Available at: <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/publications-and-resources/country-reports/vocational-education-and-training-europe-luxembourg>
- Deming, D. (2017). The growing importance of social skills in the labor market. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 132(4), 1593-1640.
- European Training Foundation (2021). Vocational education and training in the Western Balkans: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo*, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia. Available at: https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-07/ETF_WP_2021_08.pdf
- Etebefia, O.S. and Akinkumi, B.W. (2013). The Contribution of Small-Scale Industries to the National Economy. *Standard Research Journal of Business Management*, 1(2):60-71
- European Commission (2022). Vocational education and training. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/education/policies/vocational-education-training_en
- Gidado, S. D. (2014), Influence Business Education Skills in Promoting Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), in North West Geographical Zone Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development (IJARPED) VO13-14/1106*.
- Ibrahim, A. G. (2020). Sustainable small and medium enterprises in Nigeria: The role of innovation. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 8(2), 1-14.
- International Labour Organization (2021). Vocational education and training for sustainable development: A guide for policy makers. Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/skillsandemployability/publications/WCMS/lang--en/index.htm>
- Industrial Training Fund. (2021). About ITF. Retrieved from <https://www.itf.gov.ng/about-itf/>

- Iwala, O.S. (2017). Achieving Sustainable Poverty Reduction and Rural Development in Nigeria Through Local and Economic Development Strategies. *Journal of Rural Development*. 2(1):13-19. doi:10.12691/ajrd-2-1-327
- Kehinde, O. J. et al (2016). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises; Pivotal to Sustainable Economic Development: The Nigeria Experience, *International Journal of Current Research* vol. 8(1) pp 26411 – 26420, 2016.
- Adegbeniyi, A. A. (2016). The impact of human resource management practices on organizational performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 7(1), 96-109.
- International Labour Organization. (2020). World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.ilo.org/global/research/global-reports/weso/2020/lang--en/index.htm>
- Uzuagulu, A. E. (2011). Handbook on small and medium enterprise in Nigeria. African Educational Services.
- World Economic Forum. (2018). The Global Competitiveness Report 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-global-competitiveness-report-2018>
- Kpolovie, P. J. (2011). Essentials of educational technology. Port Harcourt: Wisdom Publishers.
- Kerlinger, F. N. (1975). Foundations of behavioral research. CBS College Publishing.
- Kuhn, P., & Shen, K. (2020). Do employers prefer migrant workers? Evidence from a Chinese job board. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 38(2), 373-416.
- Kram, K. E. (2019). Mentoring at work: Developmental relationships in organizational life. University Press of America.
- Miller, O. & ELuro, D. C. (2018). Impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Communication Network in Small and Medium Enterprise, Delta State. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 5(2).56-58
- Murnane, R. J. (2019). The promise and challenges of improving skill formation in the United States. *The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences*, 5(1), 3-16.
- Mwila, K. (2016). Education and Skills Development: Examining The Effectiveness Of Technical Education And Entrepreneurship Training in Solwezi District of Zambia. University of Zambia, Lusaka.
- Ndubuisi-Okolo, P. Anekwe. I. E and Attah. E. (2016) Waste Management and Sustainable Development in Nigeria: A Study of Anambra State Waste Management Agency, *European Journal of Management*, 8(17), 132-142.
- Nwankwo, O. C., & Akinola, G. O. (2021). Vocational training and youth employment in Nigeria: A case study of Oyo State. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 13(1), 1-12.
- Okoli and Okeke (2018), Extent of Strategic Human Resources Management Practices Adopted by Owners of S.M.E^s for Business Success Anambra State, Nigeria, *European Journal of Human Resources Management Studies* 3(2) 34-41
- Onukwulii, G. A., Akam, G. U & Onwuka, E. M. (2014). Challenges of Small-Scale Industries in Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 16(5) version 1, pp 19 – 25
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2021). Skills beyond school: Synthesis report. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/skills-beyond-school_9789264258704-en
- Onifade, C. O., & Akinbode, G. A. (2020). Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) and youth employment in Nigeria: A review of policies and practices. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(2), 1-12.
- Ogunyemi, O. A., & Adegbite, M. O. (2021). Small and medium enterprises and youth employment in Nigeria: The role of government policies. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 9(2), 1-12.
- Okwelle, P. C. & Ojotule, D.I. (2018). Journal of innovative and scientific and engineering –seahipaj.org
- Super, D. E. (1953). A theory of vocational development. *American psychologist*, 8(5), 185-190. doi:10.1037/h0056046
- Telbowei and Osusu (2018), Assessment of Skills Acquisition Programs in Bayalsa State: Implication for Economies Development. *Education & Science Journal of Policy Review and Curriculum Development (ESJPRCD)* 7(1)

- McGrath S. & Jo-Anna R. (2023), TVET SI: Towards Sustainable Vocational Education and Training: Thinking beyond the formal. *Southern African Journal of Environmental Education* 39, 2023. 6(3) 234-236
- Tony Elumelu Foundation. (2021). Entrepreneurship Program. Retrieved from <https://www.tonyelumelufoundation.org/programme/entrepreneurship-programme/>
- UNESCO (2019), Learning and teaching for peaceful and sustainable societies: from early childhood to primary and secondary education. Forum on education for sustainable development and global citizenship. Hanoi, Vietnam.
- United Nations Industrial Development Organization (2019). TVET for sustainable development: *A global review*. Vienna UNIDO
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021). Technical and vocational education and training for the twenty-first century: UNESCO TVET strategy. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000226230>
- United Nations Development Programme (2022). Skills Development for Inclusive and Sustainable Growth. Available at: <https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/poverty-reduction/skills-development-for-inclusive-and-sustainable-growth.html>
- Wordu, C. R., Victor, I. & Johnbull, O. O. (2018). Vocational Skills Acquisition for Entrepreneurship Development and Technological Advancement in Industrial Technology Education: A Strategic Approach to Surmount Economic Recession in Nigeria. *World Journal of Entrepreneurial Development Studies*, 2(2) 49-53
- Zhang, Y., & Zhang, J. (2021). The role of vocational education and training in reducing youth unemployment: Evidence from China. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 73(3), 329343.54